

Biostatistical Reports LUH

No. 1 / 2020

Working group Biostatistics
Institute of Cell Biology and Biophysics
Leibniz University of Hannover
and University of Copenhagen

**The maxT-test based on multiple marginal
models- a vignette to library(multcomp)**

L.A. Hothorn, F. Schaarschmidt, and Ch. Ritz

Contents

1	Properties of the maxT-test	2
2	Non-trivial multiple contrast tests	3
2.1	Interaction contrasts taking variance heterogeneity into account	3
2.2	Dunnnett-type comparison of overdispersed multinomial vectors	5
3	Modeling dose as qualitative factor or quantitative covariate	6
3.1	The Tukey trend test	6
3.2	Modeling a genotype qualitatively: restricted vs. unrestricted alternative for a continuous phenotype	7
4	Analysing multiple endpoints	9
4.1	Differently-scaled endpoints	9
4.2	Decomposition of multinomial vectors into multiple correlated binary endpoints	10
5	Joint testing of dose and time	10
5.1	Simultaneous test of dose and time	10
5.2	Using generalized estimating equations (GEE)	11
6	Inference on multiple models	12
6.1	Joint testing of tuning parameters: the poly-k issue	12
6.2	Joint testing of different test statistics	13
6.2.1	Additive or multiplicative model?	13
6.2.2	The parametric vs. nonparametric test issue	14
6.2.3	Models assuming variance heterogeneity	16
6.2.4	Analysing multi-way designs with small sample sizes	17
6.2.5	Mixing distribution as an alternative to an unimodal distribution	18
6.3	Considering several effect sizes	19
6.3.1	Why an appropriate effect size matters?	19
6.3.2	Trend test on proportions: canonical or non-canonical link function?	19
6.3.3	Dunnnett test with several effect sizes	20
7	Model selection properties of the maxT-test	22
8	Phase III randomized clinical trials: subgroups jointly analysed with the overall population	23
9	Mixed effect models	24
10	Simultaneous inference of composite endpoints with their individual endpoints	26
11	Conclusions	28

Abstract

The maxT-test using multiple marginal models is discussed by means of several real data scenarios using selected R-packages. Surprisingly different features are highlighted, among them: i) analysing different-scaled, correlated, multiple endpoints, ii) modeling dose as qualitative factor and/or quantitative covariate, iii) modeling a genotype qualitatively and / or quantitatively in GWAS, iv) comparison of overdispersed multinomial vectors, v) joint testing of dose and time, vi) joint using of different test statistics, vii) considering of several effect sizes, and viii) simultaneous inference of a composite endpoint and their individual endpoints. Introductory some properties of the maxT-test are discussed, also from a perspective of model selection.

1 Properties of the maxT-test

Not only linear forms of multiple comparison procedures, such as Dunnett test [Dun55] can be formulated as maxT-test: $\max T = \max(t_1, \dots, t_Q)$ where t_q are standardized contrast tests or more general, comparable glmm-models. The standardized (studentized) contrast test is $t_q = \sum_{i=0}^k c_i \bar{y}_i / S \sqrt{\sum_i c_i^2 / n_i}$ where c_i^q are the contrast coefficients. For a balanced design with $k = 2$ the contrast matrix, e.g. for the Williams trend test [Wil71] is:

	c_i	C	D_1	D_2
/small	c_a	-1	0	1
	c_b	-1	1/2	1/2

Table 1: Williams-type contrast matrix

The maxT-test is an union-intersection test. Its monotonicity theorem [GAB69](abbrev.): $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha} < t_{k-1,df,R,1-\alpha} < \dots < t_{k=1,df,R,1-\alpha} = t_{df,1-\alpha}$, allows individual inference, i.e. adjusted p-values, simultaneous confidence intervals, for single step procedures (which are considered here only). The maxT-test follows an univariate skewed-t distribution, which is expressed by a k-variate t-distribution $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha}$, e.g., R packages `mvtnorm` and `multcomp`. Alternatively, the conservative Bonferroni inequality (ignoring correlation), permutations [WY93], copulas [NBPD19] or multiple marginal models (mmm), where the correlation matrix is estimated from multiple glmm-models [PRB12] can be used [Hot16].

This vignette focuses on multiple marginal models (mmm). The concept of mmm [PRB12] provides the joint distribution of parameter estimates from multiple generalized linear (mixed) linear models (instead of just multiple contrast tests). The estimation of adjusted p-values and simultaneous confidence intervals is possible without the explicit formulation of the correlation matrix. The variance-covariance matrix of parameter estimates can be obtained using derivatives of the log-likelihood function in a single model, and hence for multiple models a vector of log-likelihood functions is used. This vector-valued asymptotic representation based on standardized score vectors as sum of i.i.d. normally distributed random variables. By plugging in parameter estimates, a consistent sandwich estimator of the variance-covariance matrix is obtained, i.e. the empirical covariance based on functions of the data, not on the data itself. The function `mmm` is available within the R package `multcomp` [HBW08].

In the literature and software, permutation versions of the maxT-test are dominating as a result of the pioneering book Westfall and Young [WY93] whereby the main focus are stepdown procedures in the linear model. The advantage of the maxT-mmm approach here, is it rather general formulation for any classes of glmm's. Notice, permutation version for the mixed effect model in special settings are available

now [L.19], [FB14] (e.g. in the package flip)

Because considering a broad class of glmm's- instead of contrast tests- the maxT-mmm approach is quite general. It can be used for multiple endpoints, multiple times, multiple models, etc. Before focusing on case studies with mmm in this vignette, non-trivial cases of multiple contrast tests are illustrated.

The maxT-test require marginal level α tests with monotonic superior power functions. The resampling based min-p test [WY93, WT08] fulfill the level α condition of the marginal tests by the inner-loop resampling. The properties of permutative single-step maxT and min-p tests were compared [ESD19] [DSB03]. The permutative single-step maxT requires identical distributed marginal tests [DSB03] *In the case of non-identically distributed test statistics T_j (e.g., t -statistics with different degrees of freedom), not all tests contribute equally to the max T adjusted p -values and this can lead to unbalanced adjustments* [Beran, 1988; Westfall and Young, 1993, page 50] [Wes11]. Special consonance conditions of maxT test with logical constraints were described by [BB10].

Further applications: i) the MCP-mod approach use the maxT-test as an option (as alternative to AIC) in model selection [PBGB14] (see the relation `selModel="Tmax"` option the in the CRAN package `DoseFinding`), ii) curve comparisons (see the `option="MaxT"` in the function `param.boot` in the CRAN package `curvecomp`), iii) nonparametric association between two random vectors of arbitrary dimensions decomposed in all atomic partitions and combined by Fisher or minP [BHH18] (in the function `fast.independence.test` of the CRAN package `HHG`), iv) pointwise maxT of functional data [VGPZ15], vi) multiple categorization schemes, multiple Box-Cox transformations or multiple fractional polynomial transformations for a continuous covariate [LR19], vii) maximally selected rank statistics, i.e., maximum over all possible dichotomisations of continuous variable [HL03, HZ08]. Furthermore, the model selection properties of the maxT-test are discussed below.

2 Non-trivial multiple contrast tests

2.1 Interaction contrasts taking variance heterogeneity into account

In the analysis of factorial two-way designs the interaction is often of interest, whereby the global ANOVA-interaction term is rarely interpretable, but interaction contrasts are suitable [KH14, KS15]. The `library(emmeans)` is well suited as it allows estimating differences of differences. When heterogeneous variances in unbalanced designs occur (for not too small n_i), the use of the sandwich estimator is recommended [HSH10]. Within `library(emmeans)`, this can be performed by a special version of the function `ref_grid`. As an example plant biological data were considered with factor `type` on 2 levels, and factor `dose` on three levels were selected [ZLB⁺19].

Figure 1: Interactions

Dose	emmean	SE	df	lower.CL	upper.CL
0	12.2910	1.0463	17	10.0835	14.4986
1	18.5390	1.2380	17	15.9270	21.1510
10	21.8563	1.1581	17	19.4131	24.2996

Results are averaged over the levels of: type

Confidence level used: 0.95

```

library(emmeans)
library(sandwich)
library(multcomp)
IA1<-contrast(emmeans(mod1, ~ Dose*type),
              interaction = c("tukey", "consec"), adjust="mvt")
rg1<-ref_grid(mod1, vcov. = sandwich::vcovHAC)

IAS<-contrast(emmeans(rg1, ~ Dose*type),
              interaction = c("tukey", "consec"), adjust="mvt")

```

Dose_tukey	type_consec	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
0 - 1	mutant - Col	7.55	3.24	17	2.329	0.0787
0 - 10	mutant - Col	9.01	3.12	17	2.886	0.0262
1 - 10	mutant - Col	1.46	3.39	17	0.430	0.9035

P value adjustment: mvt method for 3 tests

Table 2: IA-test assuming homogeneous variances

The low n_i and the estimated high s_i in the $[10 - 0]$ comparisons cause higher common mean square estimators with the consequence of higher p-value for the $[1 - 0]$ comparison.

Dose_tukey	type_consec	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
0 - 1	mutant - Col	7.55	2.88	17	2.619	0.0442
0 - 10	mutant - Col	9.01	2.63	17	3.422	0.0085
1 - 10	mutant - Col	1.46	3.41	17	0.428	0.9034

P value adjustment: mvt method for 3 tests

Table 3: IA-test allowing heterogeneous variances

2.2 Dunnett-type comparison of overdispersed multinomial vectors

A specific problem is the comparison of multinomial vectors, rather than the simple comparison of proportions in treatment groups versus a control [SGV17], especially when overdispersion is possible [Vog18]. As an example the number of malformed, dead or alive mice per group in the reproductive study on diethylene glycol dimethyl is used [Hot16].

Table 4: Raw data of multinomial vector

DAMID	DOSE	alive	malformed	dead
51	0	10	0	0
60	0	14	0	0
61	0	11	0	1
70	0	17	0	0
71	0	15	0	0
135	500	9	16	5
144	500	2	26	23
152	500	11	7	4
157	500	5	35	22
166	500	9	8	11
175	500	6	18	7
176	500	7	37	21
185	500	9	2	2
...	...			

Instead of the common simple 2-by-k table data, the replicate counts per dam within each dose group can be seen Table 4, with possible between dam variation, i.e. overdispersion.

Figure 2: Boxplot multinomial vector

In her thesis, Dr. Vogel (2018) provided the two functions `mcp2matrix.vglm`, `multin2mcp` (see below) which allows the analysis of `vglm`-objects in the `library(multcomp)` using the function `glht()`.

```
library(VGAM)
multivgam <- vglm(cbind(alive,malformed,dead) ~ DOSE,
family=multinomial(refLevel=1), data=bivar.re)
over<-overdispersion(multivgam)
# Multiple comparison procedure with overdispersion and simultaneous CIs
OP<-summary(glht(model = multin2mcp(multivgam, dispersion="overall"),
linfct = mcp2matrix.vglm(multivgam, linfct = mcp(DOSE = "Dunnett"))$K))
```

The global overdispersion is substantial 2.36 and therefore Dunnett-type adjusted p-value for the overdispersed multinomial vector are given in Table 23.

	lhs	estimate	se	t	p
1	malformed/alive: 62.5 - 0	-14.57	1137.62	-0.01	1.0000
2	malformed/alive: 125 - 0	1.44	1.22	1.18	0.7344
3	malformed/alive: 250 - 0	3.85	1.11	3.47	0.0038
4	malformed/alive: 500 - 0	6.03	1.10	5.49	0.0000
5	dead/alive: 62.5 - 0	0.46	0.76	0.60	0.9821
6	dead/alive: 125 - 0	1.53	0.62	2.48	0.0732
7	dead/alive: 250 - 0	1.84	0.61	2.99	0.0177
8	dead/alive: 500 - 0	4.03	0.57	7.02	0.0000

Table 5: Dunnett-type p-values: overdispersed trinomial vector

An alternative approach is the decomposition of the multinomial vector into multiple correlated binary endpoints and their joint analysis using multiple marginal models, see below.

3 Modeling dose as qualitative factor or quantitative covariate

3.1 The Tukey trend test

The literature on dose-response analysis is almost disjointly divided into methods that model the dose quantitatively (dose as a covariate in quasilinear or nonlinear models) and those that model the dose qualitatively (dose as factor in multiple contrast tests). Since there is a complex relationship between administered dose and concentration at the target, it is not clear a priori which assumption is the most appropriate. Therefore a maxT-test is indicated for models with dose as covariate or factor. By means of `mmm` this is relatively easy to do using `library(tukeytrend)` [SH20]. As covariate, the max-Test three regression models for the arithmetic, ordinal, and logarithmic-linear dose metameters is used [TCH85], for the factor, the maxTest on order restricted contrasts [Wil71] are used simultaneously. As a data example `litter`, the pup weights in three dose groups and a control in a reprotox assay is used [Wes97]. The following must be adjusted against 2 confounders (time and number) and against variance heterogeneity in this unbalanced design, as shown.

```
library(multcomp)
library(tukeytrend)
library(sandwich)
mod8 <- lm(weight ~ dosen + gesttime+number, data=litter)
tw8 <- tukeytrendfit(mod8, dose="dosen", ddf="residual",
scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog", "treat"),
```


Figure 3: Box plots litter data

```

ctype="Williams")
ex8<-summary(glht(tw8$mmm, tw8$mlf,vcov = sandwich, alternative="less"))

```

Table 6: Tukey or Williams trend test

	Variance estim.	Test statist.	<i>p</i> -value
Covariate: ari	0.002	-0.750	0.408
Covariate: ord	0.406	-1.794	0.088
Covariate: log	0.255	-1.003	0.306
Factor: 3 vs. 0	1.266	-2.112	0.045
Factor: (3+2)/2 vs. 0	0.958	-2.587	0.014
Factor: (3+2+1)/3 vs. 0	0.872	-3.194	0.002

Most in the alternative is the plateau-shape contrast: $(\mu_3 + \mu_2 + \mu_1)/3 - \mu_0$. The price of these six-variate tests compared to the Williams test seems acceptable, considering that any effect would have been overlooked in the quantitative modeling of the dose, namely the *p*-value for this plateau-shape contrasts in the above joint test 0.0022351, compared to the Williams-test $p=0.0023937$ (output not shown). The above approach works for trend test and pairwise tests accordingly.

3.2 Modeling a genotype qualitatively: restricted vs. unrestricted alternative for a continuous phenotype

Considering the genotype as a factor (with the three levels aa, Aa, or AA) either ANOVA-type test on heterogeneity without a H_1 -restriction [GD07], or specific restriction to additive, recessive or dominant alternative can be used [HH09]. From the perspective of the conflicting goals of maximum power vs. generality of the statement, is a-priori not clear which approach is the more appropriate. Therefore a maxT test over both marginal tests is indicated. The quadratic ANOVA-type test can be approximated by a contrast test in comparison to the total mean [KBBH13], and thus a uniform multiple contrast test can be formulated [HKH20]. The phenotype total cholesterol and its possible association with SNP rs7738656 is used as example [KRH16]. Because the serious heterogeneous variances in this unbalanced design, the multiple contrast is performed for the common assumption of homogeneous variances and the modification for heterogeneous variances [HSH10]

```

modQ<- lm(tc ~ genotype , data=chol)
cmatAssoc<-rbind("add"=c(-1,0,1),
                 "dom"=c(-1/2, -1/2, 1),
                 "rec"=c(-1, 1/2, 1/2))
ntab <- table(chol$genotype)
cmatGM <- contrMat(n=ntab, type="GrandMean")
cmat<-rbind(cmatAssoc,cmatGM)

AVGME<-glht(modQ,  linfct = mcp(genotype = cmat), vcov=vcovHC)
avgme<-summary(AVGME)
AVGMh<-glht(modQ,  linfct = mcp(genotype = cmat))
avgmh<-summary(AVGMh)

```

	lhs	estimate	se	t	p	Variance	Alternative
1	add	-54.4	11.68	-4.66	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
2	dom	-30.4	6.33	-4.81	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
3	rec	-51.2	11.66	-4.39	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
4	A A	51.4	11.36	4.53	0.0000	Homogenous	Unrestricted
5	A G	3.4	2.85	1.21	0.4451	Homogenous	Unrestricted
6	G G	-3.0	1.13	-2.66	0.0223	Homogenous	Unrestricted
7	add	-54.4	26.98	-2.02	0.1101	Heterogenous	Restricted
8	dom	-30.4	13.69	-2.22	0.0693	Heterogenous	Restricted
9	rec	-51.2	26.98	-1.90	0.1413	Heterogenous	Restricted
10	A A	51.4	26.35	1.95	0.1264	Heterogenous	Unrestricted
11	A G	3.4	2.79	1.24	0.4330	Heterogenous	Unrestricted
12	G G	-3.0	1.22	-2.46	0.0382	Heterogenous	Unrestricted

Table 7: Adjusted p-values for genotype as factor

Squinting at the smallest p-values is misleading here, since the tests under variance homogeneity assumption reveal a distorted liberal behavior under this pronounced variance heterogeneity, especially because of the high variance in the risk allele AA with only $n_{AA} = 12$. I.e. the proof that total cholesterol under risk allele AA is strongly increased compared to AG and/or GG is probably not to be trusted. Since the factor genotype has only 3 levels, the all pairs comparison according to Tukey would be displayed instead of the ANOVA-type GrandMean contrast as an alternative:

	lhs	estimate	se	t	p	Variance	Alternative
1	add	-54.4	11.68	-4.66	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
2	dom	-30.4	6.33	-4.81	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
3	rec	-51.2	11.66	-4.39	0.0000	Homogenous	Restricted
4	A G - A A	-48.0	11.97	-4.01	0.0002	Homogenous	Unrestricted
5	G G - A A	-54.4	11.68	-4.66	0.0000	Homogenous	Unrestricted
6	G G - A G	-6.4	3.93	-1.64	0.2253	Homogenous	Unrestricted
7	add	-54.4	26.98	-2.02	0.0959	Heterogenous	Restricted
8	dom	-30.4	13.69	-2.22	0.0592	Heterogenous	Restricted
9	rec	-51.2	26.98	-1.90	0.1244	Heterogenous	Restricted
10	A G - A A	-48.0	27.10	-1.77	0.1619	Heterogenous	Unrestricted
11	G G - A A	-54.4	26.98	-2.02	0.0958	Heterogenous	Unrestricted
12	G G - A G	-6.4	3.77	-1.71	0.1826	Heterogenous	Unrestricted

Table 8: Adjusted p-values for genotype as factor- all pairs comparisons

4 Analysing multiple endpoints

4.1 Differently-scaled endpoints

In k-sample designs is the joint simultaneous analysis for both between treatments and between primary endpoints challenging. A related $\max(\max)T$ -test, i.e. maximum over the treatments contrasts and maximum over the primary endpoint tests, uses the empirical Pearson correlation estimates between the endpoints to plug into a joint correlation matrix [HH13]. More obvious is to use both marginal models and estimate the common correlation matrix by mmm [Hot16]. Since the marginal models can be selected from the class of glmm, multiple normal, multiple binary, multiple time-to-event, etc. or even differently scaled endpoints can be analyzed. Surprisingly simple, especially from the perspective of the complex correlation matrix.

In the following, the pup weights and malformation incidences as a possible reprotoxicological response to the administration of increasing doses of ethylene glycol to mice are analyzed simultaneously. Thus, bivariate correlated normal-distributed variables and a binary variable are analyzed, whereby the dose is modeled as a covariate.

Figure 4: Ethylen glycol example.

In the ethylene glycol example the three objects w_N , w_O , w_{LL} contain the parameter estimates of linear models for the normal distributed endpoint `Weight` and further the three objects p_N , p_O , p_{LL} containing the parameter estimates of generalized linear models with binomial link functions for the binary endpoint `Malformation`.

```
library(multcomp)
wuleon$dose<-as.factor(wuleon$Dose)
Dlevelw<-as.numeric(levels(wuleon$dose))
SOW<-log(Dlevelw[2]) -
log(Dlevelw[3]/Dlevelw[2]) * (Dlevelw[2]-Dlevelw[1]) / (Dlevelw[3]-Dlevelw[2])
wuleon$DoseN<-as.numeric(as.character(wuleon$dose))
wuleon$DoseO<-as.numeric(wuleon$dose)
wuleon$DoseL<-log(wuleon$DoseN)
wuleon$DoseLL<-wuleon$DoseL
wuleon$DoseLL[wuleon$DoseN==Dlevelw[1]] <-SOW
```

```

wN <-lm(Weight~DoseN, data=wuleon)
wO <-lm(Weight~DoseO, data=wuleon)
wLL <-lm(Weight~DoseLL, data=wuleon)

pN <-glm(Malformation~DoseN, family=binomial(), data=wuleon)
pO <-glm(Malformation~DoseO, family=binomial(), data=wuleon)
pLL <-glm(Malformation~DoseLL, family=binomial(), data=wuleon)

wuWeMa <- glht(mmm(covarWe=wN, ordinWe=wO, linlogWe=wLL,
                  covarMa=pN, ordinMa=pO, linlogMa=pLL),
              mlf(covarWe="DoseN=0", ordinWe="DoseO=0", linlogWe="DoseLL=0",
                  covarMa="DoseN=0", ordinMa="DoseO=0", linlogMa="DoseLL=0"))

```

Table 9: Tukey Trend Test for Joint Modeling of Normal and Binomial Endpoint

	Test stats	<i>p</i> -value
Weight: ari	-28.69	0.0000
Weight: ord	-30.63	0.0000
Weight: log	-30.63	0.0000
Malform: ari	14.64	0.0000
Malform: ord	14.24	0.0000
Malform: log	14.24	0.0000

Dose-dependent highly significant weight retardation and significant increase in malformation rates (for ordinal dose scores) are evident.

4.2 Decomposition of multinomial vectors into multiple correlated binary endpoints

An alternative to simultaneous inference between overdispersed multinomial vectors is to decompose them into multiple correlated binary endpoints [Hot16] following the individualized regressions as an alternative to polychotomous logistic regression [BG84].

```

library(multcomp)
mL1<-glm(cbind(malformed, alive)~DOSE, data=bivar.re,
         family = quasibinomial(), na.action="na.exclude")
mL2<-glm(cbind(dead, alive)~DOSE, data=bivar.re,
         family = quasibinomial(), na.action="na.exclude")
mL12 <- glht(mmm(mal = mL1, dead= mL2), mlf(mcp(DOSE = "Dunnett")),
            alternative="greater")

```

Similar *p*-values result in this special bivariate analysis compared to the above overdispersed multinomial approach.

5 Joint testing of dose and time

5.1 Simultaneous test of dose and time

Simultaneous inference for a set of contrasts (linear combinations) of means in longitudinal scenarios. Computes multiplicity-adjusted *p*-values and simultaneous confidence intervals for comparing groups at multiple time points by combining time-point-specific marginal models by the R package `SimLongi`.

Table 10: Bivariate multiple binary endpoints- Dunnett-type p-values

	Test statist.	adj p-value
Malformed/alive: 62-0	-0.01	0.8684
Malformed/alive: 125-0	1.15	0.3762
Malformed/alive: 250-0	3.38	0.0019
Malformed/alive: 500-0	5.35	0.0000
Dead/alive: 62-0	0.58	0.6466
Dead/alive: 125-0	2.39	0.0370
Dead/alive: 250-0	2.89	0.0096
Dead/alive: 500-0	6.78	0.0000

```
#library(remotes)
#install_github("PhilipPallmann/SimLongi")
library(SimLongi)
data(heart)
SMM<-SimLongiMMM(data=heart, response="heartrate", group="drug",
  time="time", id="person", type="Dunnett",
  base=3, reldist="t")$Results
```

Table 11: Simultaneous Dunnett-type treatment comparison per time point

	Estimate	SE	Lower	Upper	Statistic	P
T1:ax23 - control	-2.25	2.76	-9.89	5.39	-0.81	0.8832
T1:bww9 - control	9.00	2.97	0.78	17.22	3.03	0.0289
T2:ax23 - control	8.12	3.13	-0.54	16.79	2.59	0.0703
T2:bww9 - control	11.62	3.56	1.78	21.47	3.27	0.0174
T3:ax23 - control	9.50	2.79	1.77	17.23	3.40	0.0129
T3:bww9 - control	7.12	3.27	-1.91	16.16	2.18	0.1544
T4:ax23 - control	2.12	2.86	-5.78	10.03	0.74	0.9160
T4:bww9 - control	8.75	2.95	0.60	16.90	2.97	0.0326

A modified version for small sample sizes is available [PRH18].

5.2 Using generalized estimating equations (GEE)

Simultaneous inference for different-scaled correlated multiple endpoints in the presence of repeated observations generalized estimating equation model is fit for each endpoint marginally, taking into account dependencies within the same subject, available in the R package `mmmgee` [RHRP19].

```
library(mmmgee)
data(keratosis)
m1<-geem2(clearance~trt, id=id, data=keratosis,
  family=binomial, corstr="independence")
m2<-geem2(pain~trt, id=id, data=keratosis[keratosis$lesion==1, ],
  family=gaussian, corstr="exchangeable")
L1<-L2<-diag(1, 4) [-1, ]
```

```
MGE<-mmmgee.test(x=list(m1,m2),L=list(L1,L2),alternative="less",
                 conf.int=TRUE,denomDF=40,statistic="Wald",
                 type="maximum",biascorr=TRUE,
                 asymptotic=FALSE,closed.test=TRUE)
mge<-as.data.frame(MGE$test$closed.test)[,c(2,5)]
```

Table 12: Bivariate repeated measures: Dunnett-type using mmmgee

	Estimate	adj p-value
Clearance: B-A	0.08	0.6613
Clearance: C-A	-0.27	0.1353
Clearance: D-A	-1.07	0.0000
Pain: B-A	-1.04	0.0000
Pain: C-A	-1.14	0.0000
Pain: D-A	-1.99	0.0000

6 Inference on multiple models

6.1 Joint testing of tuning parameters: the poly-k issue

Tumor rates are compared in long-term carcinogenicity bioassays by means of trend tests. A mortality-adjusted analysis is recommended [Kod12], because longer living animals may develop tumors more likely than those dying earlier. The poly-k adjustment [BP88] is simple, does not need cause-of-death information and is robust to different tumor lethality patterns [MAK05]. It accounts for the dose-specific mortality by individual weights $w_{ij} = (t_{ij}/t_{max})^k$ reflecting individual mortality pattern (t_{ij} is time of death of animal j in dose i). The tuning parameter k is data-dependent and is used in parallel $k = 3$ and $k = 6$ [SAH]. The weights result in adjusted sample sizes $n_i^* = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{ij}$ to be used instead of the randomized number of animals n_i . Therefore adjusted proportions $p_i^* = y_i/n_i^*$ are used instead of the crude tumor proportions $p_i = y_i/n_i$. As an example the NTP study on the carcinogenic potential of methyleugenol for the incidence of skin fibromas is used [NTP00]. By means of the CRAN package MCPAN the w_{ij}, n_i^*, p_i^* can be easily estimated. Here, a max(maxT)-test is proposed: maximum over three scores-specific regression models, the three Williams-type contrasts and for the tuning parameters $k = 3, 6$.

```
##### poly-k
library(MCPAN)
data("methyl", package="MCPAN")
data(methyl)
me <- methyl
# death: time of death, max(death)=length of study = 730 days
# poly-3 adjustment: (time of death/max(time))^k, k=3,
# for those animals without tumour at time of death!
# Compute the poly-3 (-k)- weights at the level of single animals
me$weightpoly3 <- 1
me$weightpoly6 <- 1
# Animals without tumour at time of death get corrected sample size
wt0 <- which(me$tumour == 0)
me$weightpoly3[wt0] <- (me$death[wt0]/max(me$death))^3
me$weightpoly6[wt0] <- (me$death[wt0]/max(me$death))^6
me$dosegroup <- me$group
```

```

levels(me$dosegroup) <- c("0", "37", "75", "150")
me$dose <- as.numeric(as.character(me$dosegroup))
# Notice, the Model use an identity link for difference to control,
fitpoly3 <- glm(tumour ~ dose, data=me, family=binomial(link="identity"),
               weight=weightpoly3)
fitpoly6 <- glm(tumour ~ dose, data=me, family=binomial(link="identity"),
               weight=weightpoly6)
library(tukeytrend)
ttpoly3 <- tukeytrendfit(fitpoly3, dose="dose",
                       scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog", "treat"), ctype="Williams")
ttpoly6 <- tukeytrendfit(fitpoly6, dose="dose",
                       scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog", "treat"), ctype="Williams")
compttpoly6 <- glht(model=ttpoly6$mmm, linfct=ttpoly6$mlf, alternative="greater")
tt36 <- combtt(ttpoly3, ttpoly6)
TT36 <- summary(asglht(tt36, alternative="greater"))

```

Table 13: Tukey-Williams-type trend test models for poly k=3 and k=6

Comparisons	Test stats	p-value
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.doseari: doseari	1.77	0.0876
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.doseord: doseord	2.50	0.0177
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.dosearilog: dosearilog	2.48	0.0189
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 1	1.91	0.0668
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 2	3.03	0.0040
ttpoly3.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 3	3.83	0.0002
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.doseari: doseari	2.32	0.0276
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.doseord: doseord	2.98	0.0048
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.dosearilog: dosearilog	2.96	0.0050
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 1	2.08	0.0470
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 2	3.18	0.0027
ttpoly6.glm.tumour.dosetreat: C 3	3.97	0.0002

Most in the alternative is the plateau-type Williams contrast for poly-6 adjustment, where as the difference to poly-3 is tiny in this particular example. Another example for multiple tuning parameters is the use of a grid of shift parameters for logarithmic transformation including zero dose values; see section 3.1.5 in [SH20].

6.2 Joint testing of different test statistics

[GYM13] proposing permutation minP-test: *For linear regression, should the model include a covariate that uses a large fraction of the total degrees of freedom? If the covariate is noise, then its degrees of freedom are wasted. What about data transformations? Should a continuous covariate be, say, log-transformed? Should the response variable also be transformed?*

6.2.1 Additive or multiplicative model?

Transformation of the primary endpoint is a common-used approach, among them especially the log-transformation, with the aim of robustification against extreme values, yielding variance homogeneity, achieving a smaller p-value in inference. On the other hand log-transformation changes from an additive model into a multiplicative model. Here, we consider the simplest case of a maxT-test for a Dunnett-type approach with the untransformed and the log-transformed endpoint. Based on the creatine kinase endpoint in a chronic toxicity bioassay, this maxT-test is compared with the most likely transformation model [HMB18], considering all possible transformations.

```

library(multcomp)
library(mlt)
yCK <- numeric_var("CreatKinase", support =
  quantile(ClinCK$CreatKinase, prob = c(.01, .99)))
yC <- Bernstein_basis(yCK, ui = "increasing",
  order = 5) # Bernstein polynomial

mC <- ctm(yC, shifting = ~ dose, todistr = "Logistic", data = ClinCK) # condit transf mod
mC_mlt <- mlt(mC, data = ClinCK) # most likely transformation
K <- diag(length(coef(mC_mlt))) # contrast matrix
rownames(K) <- names(coef(mC_mlt))
matr <- bstorder+1
K <- K[-(1:(5+1)),] # for order 5 Bernstein
C <- glht(mC_mlt, linfct = K) # MLT-Dunnett-type test
COR <- 1/exp(confint(C)$confint)
mML <- summary(C)
library(ggplot2)
mml <- fortify(mML)

ClinCK$LogCK <- log(ClinCK$CreatKinase)
mod1 <- lm(CreatKinase ~ dose, data = ClinCK)
mod2 <- lm(LogCK ~ dose, data = ClinCK)
mBV <- glht(mmm(CreatKinase = mod1, LogCK = mod2),
  mlf(mcp(dose = "Dunnett")))

```

	Test statist.	p-value
Untran: 62-0	1.71	0.36815
Untran: 125-0	1.02	0.83620
Untran: 250-0	1.49	0.51623
Untran: 500-0	2.44	0.08096
Untran: 1000-0	3.53	0.00292
Log-tran: 62-0	1.85	0.28830
Log-tran: 125-0	2.05	0.19702
Log-tran: 250-0	2.76	0.03514
Log-tran: 500-0	4.01	0.00051
Log-ntran: 1000-0	5.03	0.00000
mlt-tran: 62-0	-1.33	0.50558
mlt-tran: 125-0	-2.21	0.09929
mlt-tran: 250-0	-2.98	0.01252
mlt-tran: 500-0	-4.38	0.00004
mlt-tran: 1000-0	-5.08	0.00000

Table 14: Comparing maxT-test(untransf, log-transf) vs. mlt-Dunnett type test: 2-sided p-values

Notice, the p-values for untransformed and log-transformed comparisons are adjusted against both multiple comparisons and transformations. Notice, the widely used log-transformation in Dunnett-test is problematic [Sch13].

6.2.2 The parametric vs. nonparametric test issue

The simple question of whether a parametric test or a nonparametric test better represents the effect difference can be answered by a permutation maximum test [Neu15]. This can be generalized to the k-sample problem and the Dunnett test by an asymptotic maximum test using the mmm approach where two models with the original endpoint and its rank-transformation are considered. Thus one chooses between

the difference of expected values or rank difference as effect size. As an example, the mice data example with the primary endpoint reaction time [SHI87] is used here.

```
## Loading required package: mvtnorm
## Loading required package: survival
##
## Attaching package: 'survival'
## The following object is masked _by_ '.GlobalEnv':
##
##   heart
## Loading required package: TH.data
## Loading required package: MASS
##
## Attaching package: 'TH.data'
## The following object is masked from 'package:MASS':
##
##   geyser
##
## Attaching package: 'multcomp'
## The following object is masked _by_ '.GlobalEnv':
##
##   litter
```


Figure 5: Boxplot reaction time example.

```
reaction$CSS <- (rank(reaction$Time) / (length(reaction$Time) + 1)) ^ 3 #Lehman
library(coin, warn.conflicts = FALSE, quietly = TRUE)
reaction$R <- rnk_trafo(reaction$Time, ties.method = "mid-ranks")
reaction$N <- normal_trafo(reaction$Time, ties.method = "mid-ranks")
reaction$M <- median_trafo(reaction$Time, mid.score = "0.5")
reaction$S <- savage_trafo(reaction$Time, ties.method = "mid-ranks")
reaction$C <- consal_trafo(reaction$Time, ties.method = "mid-ranks", a = 3)
reaction$K <- koziol_trafo(reaction$Time, ties.method = "mid-ranks", j = 1)
mp <- lm(Time ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnp <- lm(R ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnpN <- lm(N ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnpM <- lm(M ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnpS <- lm(S ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnpC <- lm(C ~ Dose, data = reaction)
mnpK <- lm(K ~ Dose, data = reaction)
```

```
mnpCSS<-lm(CSS~Dose, data=reaction)
jm<-glht(mmm(Para=mp, NonPara=mnpK), mlf(mcp(Dose="Dunnett")))
```

The increase of the adjusted p-values considering 2 or even 3 models is tiny.

```
#####mlt
library(mlt)
bstorder<-5
yRT <- numeric_var("Time", support =
                    quantile(reaction$Time, prob = c(.01, .99)))
yR <- Bernstein_basis(yRT, ui = "increasing",
                     order =5) # Bernstein polynomial

mR <- ctm(yR, shifting = ~ Dose, todistr = "Logistic", data =reaction) # condit transf mod
mR_mlt<-mlt(mR, data = reaction) # most likely transformation
KR <- diag(length(coef(mR_mlt))) # contrast matrix
rownames(KR) <- names(coef(mR_mlt))
matr<-bstorder+1
KR <- KR[-(1:(5+1)),] # for order 5 Bernstein
CR<-glht(mR_mlt, linfct = KR) # MLT-Dunnett-type test
mMR<-summary(CR)
library(ggplot2)
mmr<-fortify(mMR) [, c(1,5,6)]
```

```
library(nparcomp)
Koni<-nparcomp(Time ~Dose, data=reaction, asy.method = "probit",
               type = "Dunnett", alternative = "two.sided",
               plot.simci = FALSE, info = FALSE, correlation=FALSE)
KONI<-Koni$Analysis[, c(5,6)]
colnames(KONI) <-c("Test statist.", "adj p-value")
```

Table 15: Parametric, Koziol-scores, mlt and relative effect size Dunnett-type tests

	Test statist.	adj p-value
Para: 1-0	2.20	0.11036
Para: 2-0	3.20	0.00589
Para: 3-0	4.80	0.00000
Koziol: 1-0	-3.15	0.00738
Koziol: 2-0	-3.90	0.00077
Koziol: 3-0	-5.38	0.00000
mlt: 1-0	-2.63	0.02308
mlt: 2-0	-3.18	0.00418
mlt: 3-0	-4.27	0.00007
RelEff: 1-0	2.94	0.00994
RelEff: 2-0	2.85	0.01289
RelEff: 3-0	3.37	0.00224

Not surprisingly, quite different conclusions are reached depending on the choice of model.

6.2.3 Models assuming variance heterogeneity

Variance heterogeneities is common and can cause both size and power problems, especially in unbalanced designs. In the following, five very different approaches were chosen for the nitrofen data set: i) the simple linear model (mod1), the modeling of the variance on average using a generalized least

square model `gls(mod2)`, iii) continuous outcome logistic regression (mod2), iv) using sandwich estimator (mod4) [HSH10], v) Welch-type *df* (mod5) [HH08]. With regard to the relevant small n_i behavior is currently still unclear, which approach is to be recommended.

```
data("nitrofen", package="boot")
nitrof <- nitrofen[, c(1, 5)]
nitrof$Conc <- as.factor(nitrof$conc)
library(multcomp)
library(nlme)
library(sandwich)
library(SimComp)
library(tram)
mod1 <- lm(total ~ Conc, data=nitrof)
mod2 <- nlme::gls(total ~ Conc - 1, weights=varIdent(form=~1|Conc), data=nitrof)
mod3 <- Colr(total ~ Conc, data=nitrof) # COLR
mod4 <- glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(Conc = "Dunnett"), vcov = vcovHC)
mod5 <- SimTestDiff(total ~ Conc, data=nitrof, type="Dunnett", covar.equal=FALSE)
```

6.2.4 Analysing multi-way designs with small sample sizes

In a small sample size two-way design where a non-significant secondary factor requires a high *df*, the multiple comparisons between the levels of the primary factor may be more sensitive in a pseudo one-way layout. But which model is more appropriate is a priori unknown, and therefore a MaxT-test over these candidate models can be used. As an teaching example, the cholesterol example [Wes99] was modified (lesser sample size, without drugE, with a virtual, non-significant) secondary age class factor:

Figure 6: Boxplots cholesterol example.

```

mod1<-lm(response~trt, data=cholest)
mod2<-lm(response~trt+age, data=cholest)# 2way model without interaction
cM<-contrMat(n=c(7,7,7,7), type = "Dunnnett", base = 4)
mLB <- glht(mmm(Oneway = mod1, Twoway= mod2), mlf(mcp(trt =cM)))
mlb<-summary(mLB)

```

	lhs	t	p
1	Oneway: 1 - 4	-6.82	0.00000
2	Oneway: 2 - 4	-4.41	0.00003
3	Oneway: 3 - 4	-2.54	0.04339
4	Twoway: 1 - 4	-6.63	0.00000
5	Twoway: 2 - 4	-4.23	0.00020
6	Twoway: 3 - 4	-2.30	0.07835

Table 16: One-way vs. two-way ANOVA based Dunnnett-tests

In this particular example, the pseudo one-way analysis provides smaller Dunnnett-type p-values compared with the textbook style two-way analysis.

6.2.5 Mixing distribution as an alternative to an unimodal distribution

The overwhelming majority assumes unimodal distributions for k-sample inference: normal or continuous non-normal distribution. However, some biological models support a responder/nonresponder behavior, i.e. a mixing distribution. Different models can be used for this scenario: i) one allows increased variances under treatments (especially for small n_i), ii) one estimates the bimodal distributions and analyzes only the responder fraction [Hot16], iii) one takes rank transformations that are sensitive to responder/nonresponder, e.g. for Lehmann alternative [LEH63] or Conover-scores [CS88]. What they all have in common is that it is not possible to know a-priori whether real data follows a mixing distributions, nor which particular transformation is the best alternative. Using comet assay data [Hot16], a maxT-t test is demonstrated, which simultaneously considers a mlt-Lehmann model, Conover rank scores and a linear model:

Figure 7: Boxplot Comet Assay

Assuming linear regression on sample, cell level data

```

library(multcomp); library(tram); library(coin)
TIComet$Dose <- as.numeric(as.character(factor(TIComet$Treatment,
      levels=c("VC", "Low", "medium", "High", "Superhigh"),
      labels=c("0", "2.5", "5", "10", "50"))))

TIComet$C<-consal_trafo(TIComet$Tail.intensity, ties.method = "mid-ranks", a = 3)
ML<-Lehmann(Tail.intensity~Dose, data=TIComet, support=c(0.01,100), order=5)
MN<-lm(Tail.intensity~Dose, data=TIComet)
MC<-lm(C~Dose, data=TIComet)
JM<-mmm(l=as.mlt(ML), n=MN, c=MC)
jm<-summary(glht(mmm(Leh=as.mlt(ML), ConS=MC, LM=MN), mlf("Dose=0")))

```

Table 17: Comet assay assuming mixing distribution: 3 different test principles

lhs	t	p
Leh: Dose	20.31	0.00000
ConS: Dose	28.04	0.00000
LM: Dose	27.25	0.00000

6.3 Considering several effect sizes

6.3.1 Why an appropriate effect size matters?

Particularly in the interpretation of inference in the biosciences, the predominant use of p-values (or stars in figures) made the effect size somewhat secondary, even hidden. This changes the paradigm shift of [AGM19], away from dichotomizing at the 5% false positive rate to the primary interpretation of the effect size and its interval, denoted as compatibility interval.

But what effect size? If you follow the common-used $\mu_{Novum} - \mu_{Verum}$, or you use the odds ratio (OR) as universal effect size, optimally dichotomized by continuous outcome logistic regression [LRFH41], or you choose the ‚best’ effect size from a set of meaningful effect sizes, i.e. the one that lies most in the alternative- data-dependent. Impossible! Since we have learned to determine the effect size very a priori- dependent of the design, the randomisation, the aim, the distribution etc.- , and now suddenly even post-hoc? The latter follows the idea of being as compatible as possible with the data, assumptions and models. The workhorse is the T_{max} test (an UIT), but this time over any glmm model by using multiple marginal model approach [PRB12].

This is a somewhat provocative approach: the decision on the effect size of the interest only after the data has been collected. This contradicts all kinds of pre-specification and registration of clinical trials (e.g. clinicaltrials.gov). Is it possible that these concepts were defined long before it was possible to consider the costs of conducting multiple inferences? This is exactly what we are proposing here.

Two case studies will illustrate this approach in the following: i) trend test on proportions, ii) Dunnett tests with several effect size.

6.3.2 Trend test on proportions: canonical or non-canonical link function?

The canonical link function in the glm is the logit with the odds ratio as effect size. Alternatively the non-canonical links yielding risk difference or risk ratio as effect size are available. Here we propose a related T_{max} test over three selected glm models with different link functions yielding different effect sizes.

This approach will be demonstrated by simple 2-by-k-table for the incidence of squamous cell papilloma in male B6C3F1 mice administered 0, 0.0875, 0.175, 0.35, or 0.70 mM acrylamide [BMO⁺13]. When the control rate is zero and, or small sample sizes occur, the add-1 adjustment can be recommended [SSH08, AR10] yielding pseudo-score intervals. A Tukey-type trend test is used where the dose levels are modeled quantitatively using a maximum test on arithmetic, ordinal and logarithmic dose scores [SH20]. I.e. a double maximum test is used, over the three models with different link function and the three regression models. The joint distribution under the null for this complex maximum test is achieved by means of multiple marginal models (mmm) [PRB12].

	Dose	0	0.0875	0.175	0.35	0.70
No. papilloma		0	2	2	6	6
No. mice		46	45	46	47	44

```
squam<-data.frame(
  dose = c(0,0.0875, 0.175, 0.35, 0.70),
  events = c(0, 2,2,6,6),
  n = c(46, 45, 46, 47,44))
library(tukeytrend)
swaOR <-glm(cbind(events+0.5, (n-events)+0.5)~dose, data=squam,
  family= binomial(link="logit"))#
tuOR <- tukeytrendfit(swaOR, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
cOR <- exp(confint(glht(model=tuOR$mmm, linfct=tuOR$mlf, alternative="greater"))$confint)
```

Although the use of `library(addreg)` to fit additive identity-link binomial regression models using a stable combinatorial EM algorithm [DM15] is a more general approach, risk difference as effect size can be under some conditions also used by common GLM with identity link.

`library(logbin)` fits relative risk regression models using the log-binomial model [DM15]. The multiple marginal model approach [PRB12] allows a maximum test over models, here over the three common effect sizes odds ratio, risk ratio and risk difference.

```
library(tukeytrend)
library(logbin, quietly=TRUE)
swaOR <-glm(cbind(events+0.5, (n-events)+0.5)~dose, data=squam,
  family= binomial(link="logit"))#
tuOR <- tukeytrendfit(swaOR, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pOR <- summary(glht(model=tuOR$mmm, linfct=tuOR$mlf, alternative="greater"))
swaRD <- glm(formula(swaOR), data = squam, family=binomial(link="identity"),maxit=500)
tuRD <- tukeytrendfit(swaRD, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pRD <- summary(glht(model=tuRD$mmm, linfct=tuRD$mlf, alternative="greater"))
swaRR<-logbin(cbind(events, (n-events))~dose, data=squam, warn=FALSE)
tuRR <- tukeytrendfit(swaRR, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pRR <- summary(glht(model=tuRR$mmm, linfct=tuRR$mlf, alternative="greater"))
ttany <- combtt(tuOR, tuRD,tuRR)
anylink<-summary(glht(model=ttany$mmm, linfct=ttany$mlf, alternative="greater"))
```

The optimal model without a-priori model choice (Opt: RD) is for RD and $\log(D_i)$, where the p-value of 0.0013 is only slightly higher than for the a-priori selected model (0.00068).

6.3.3 Dunnett test with several effect sizes

Four particular effect sizes are used for the endpoint creatin kinase jointly, i.e. the parametric linear model, the continuous logistic regression, the Lehmann alternative and Cox proportional hazard model [Hot19]:

Table 18: Any effect size, any metameter

Effect size	Metameter	<i>p</i> -value
OR	ari	0.0084432283594037
OR	ord	0.00609218925492327
OR	log	0.00614464202784171
RD	ari	0.0027786882654357
RD	ord	0.000714075084365828
RD	log	0.000686962017920845
RR	ari	0.00606816597757942
RR	ord	0.00433540959805323
RR	log	0.00469988341983629
Opt:RD	Opt:log	0.00129288406774863

```

library(mlt)
library(multcomp)
library(sandwich)
library(tram)
ClinCKK$dose<-as.factor(ClinCKK$Dose) # defining dose as factor
mL<-lm(CreatKinase~dose, data=ClinCKK)
mC<-Colr(CreatKinase~dose, data=ClinCKK, support=c(100,900), add=c(-100,100), order=15)
mH<-Coxph(CreatKinase~dose, data=ClinCKK, support=c(100,900), add=c(-100,100), order=15)
mL<-Lehmann(CreatKinase~dose, data=ClinCKK, support=c(100,900), add=c(-100,100), order=15)
library(sandwich)
bread.mlt<-function(x)vcov(x)*nrow(x$data)
K<-glht(mL, linfct=mcp(dose="Dunnett"))$linfct
KK<-matrix(0,nrow=ncol(K), ncol=length(coef(as.mlt(mL))))
KK[,grep("dose", names(coef(as.mlt(mL))))]<-K
rownames(KK)<-rownames(K)
JM<-mmm(l=as.mlt(mL), c=as.mlt(mC), h=as.mlt(mH))
mjj<-glht(JM, linfct=mlf(KK))

```

	Test statist.	adj p-value
Lehman: 62-0	1.22	0.80014
Lehman: 125-0	2.37	0.12697
Lehman: 250-0	3.09	0.01833
Lehman: 500-0	4.58	0.00004
Lehman: 1000-0	5.47	0.00000
COLR: 62-0	-1.27	0.76737
COLR: 125-0	-2.09	0.22998
COLR: 250-0	-2.87	0.03558
COLR: 500-0	-4.31	0.00018
COLR: 1000-0	-4.95	0.00001
CoxPH: 62-0	-1.92	0.32015
CoxPH: 125-0	-1.90	0.33093
CoxPH: 250-0	-2.63	0.06859
CoxPH: 500-0	-3.75	0.00174
CoxPH: 1000-0	-4.13	0.00048

Table 19: Dunnett-type test covering 3 different effect sizes

7 Model selection properties of the maxT-test

The simple question "is that model with $\min(p^{adj}) < 0.05$ the best model?" is not obvious and easy to answer. First, because of the monotonicity characteristics of the maxT-test individual decisions, such as a simultaneous confidence interval for a selected contrast or an adjusted p-value for a specific model are available. Secondly, there is no best model (let alone a true model) simply because "G. Box: all models are wrong, some are useful". Thirdly, maxT-test is not a model selection approach. Fourthly, commonly > 1 model reveal $(p^{adj}) < 0.05$, and these p-values are often in the same magnitude, i.e. it is more likely that a set of models is appropriate, instead of just one. Fifthly, the diagnostic properties of maxT test are discussed [COX77].

In the maxT-test examples above, one selects the most suitable of several candidate models, actually a classic model selection problem. Since maxT-test becomes more and more conservative with increasing number of models and decreasing correlation, this is an excellent alternative method. But even a model comparison based on different endpoints becomes difficult. This is illustrated by the example of liver weights, where different body weights sometimes have to be considered.

```
mod1<-lm(LiverWt~Dose, data=liv)
mod2<-lm(LiverWt~Dose+BodyWt, data=liv)
mod3<-lm(relLiv~Dose, data=liv)
anova(mod1,mod2,mod3)
anova(mod1,mod2)
library(MuMIn)
MuMIn::model.sel(mod1, mod2, mod3)
mLiv <- glht(mmm(OneF = mod1, COVAR= mod2, RelWt=mod3), mlf(mcp(Dose = "Dunnett"))))
MLIV<-summary(mLiv)
```

	Test statist.	adj p-value
Dose only: 62-0	-1.48	0.58568
Dose only: 125-0	1.38	0.66213
Dose only: 250-0	-0.96	0.91771
Dose only: 500-0	-4.21	0.00033
Dose only: 1000-0	-5.00	0.00000
Dose+BWt: 62-0	-1.00	0.90138
Dose+BWt: 125-0	1.09	0.85216
Dose+BWt: 250-0	-1.36	0.67375
Dose+BWt: 500-0	-3.94	0.00067
Dose+BWt: 1000-0	-2.09	0.21543
RelWt: 62-0	-1.21	0.77916
RelWt: 125-0	1.29	0.72154
RelWt: 250-0	-1.22	0.77381
RelWt: 500-0	-4.56	0.00009
RelWt: 1000-0	-3.77	0.00153

Table 20: Dunnett-type test covering 3 model with different endpoint

8 Phase III randomized clinical trials: subgroups jointly analysed with the overall population

A priori defined subgroups, such as age cohort, biomarker strata, may improve the efficacy claim in RCT-additional to the analysis of the overall population. Many strategies exist for the complex interaction between subgroup-specific (targeted and non-targeted) and overall population analysis. A rather specific version is the simultaneous analysis of both the subgroups and the total population taking the correlation between these multiple test statistics into account [AH09]. A further characteristic of these phase III studies is the claim for multiple, correlated, primary endpoints. By means of the multiple marginal model approach (mmm) the joint inference can be easily formulated [Vog20].

As an example, the randomized two-arm trial Apixaban vs. Aspirin to treat stroke, i.e. ischaemic, haemorrhagic, or unspecified, in patients with atrial fibrillation where 2 subgroups are used: S1 (previous stroke or transient ischaemic attack), S2 (no previous stroke or TIA) [DEC⁺12]:

		Global		S1		S2		
Treatment	Endpoint	no Event	Event	no Event	Event	no Event	Event	
/small	Apixaban	Ischaemic	2764	43	381	9	2383	34
	Aspirin		2692	97	347	27	2345	70
	Apixaban	Hemorrhag	2801	6	389	1	2412	5
	Aspirin		2780	9	370	4	2410	5
	Apixaban	Stroke	2758	49	380	10	2378	39
	Aspirin		2684	105	344	30	2340	75

Table 21: Number of events for 3 primary endpoints, the overall and the both subgroup population in the Apixaban vs. Aspirin trial

First, the 9 marginal logistic models are fitted (for the 3 endpoints and the 3 populations), where NA's in the data are used to characterize subpopulations:

```
f1<-glm(Ischaemic ~ Treatment, data=nh, family=binomial())
f2<-glm(Hemorhag ~ Treatment, data=nh, family=binomial())
f3<-glm(Stroke ~ Treatment, data=nh, family=binomial())
f4 <- glm(IschnoTIA~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
f5 <- glm(HemnoTIA~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
f6<- glm(StrokenoTIA~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
f7 <- glm(IT~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
f8 <- glm(HT~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
f9 <- glm(ST~Treatment, data = nh, na.action = na.exclude,
          family = binomial)
```

The estimation of the lower simultaneous confidence limits for the two-sample comparison (performed by the Dunnett-test) is quite simple using the mmm-approach:

```

library(multcomp)
msCI <- glht(mmm(f1, f2, f3, f4, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9),
             mlf(mcp(Treatment = "Dunnett")), alternative="greater")
CAX<-exp(confint(msCI) $confint[1:9, 1:2])

```

	Odds ratio	Lower confidence limit
Overall ischaemic	2.32	1.49
Overall hemorhag	1.51	0.43
Overall stroke	2.20	1.45
No TIA ischaemic	2.09	1.27
No TIA hemorhag	1.00	0.22
No TIA stroke	1.95	1.22
TIA ischaemic	3.29	1.30
TIA hemorhag	4.21	0.30
TIA stroke	3.31	1.37

Table 22: Simultaneous global and subgroup Dunnett-type tests

Apixaban reduced in comparison to Apsirin the risk of stroke and ischaemic stroke in the overall population and in both subgroups, but no further benefit can be demonstrated for the efficacy endpoint of haemorrhagic stroke.

9 Mixed effect models

In addition to the primary factor (or primary covariate), other factors are considered, some of which are random factors, such as repeated measurements over time or technical replicates on the same experimental unit. This can be done with a (g)lmm, where simultaneous inference of these objects is available asymptotically due to the approach of general parametric models [HBW08]. A specific random factor is modeling the dependence of pups within a litter in reproductive toxicology bioassay, as shown here in the example using behavioral data with a control and three doses [Hot16].

Figure 8: Boxplots behavioral data.

Therefore the assumption of variance homogeneity seems not to be appropriate. Below linear mixed models with and without random intercepts, with and without sex as a covariate, and with or without assuming dose-specific variance are fitted and the control group is compared to the medium dose.

```
library(nlme, quietly = TRUE)
library(lme4, quietly = TRUE)

##
## Attaching package: 'lme4'
## The following object is masked from 'package:nlme':
##
##   lmList

library(tukeytrend)

mixedm1 <- lmer(Olfactory ~ Dose + (1|Litter), data = ragazz)
lm1 <- lmer2lm(mixedm1)

mixedm2 <- lme(Olfactory ~ Dose, random=~Sex|Litter,
               weights = varIdent(form=~1|Dose), data=ragazz)
lm2 <- lmer2lm(mixedm2)

mixedm3 <- lmer(Olfactory ~ Dose + Sex + (1|Litter), data = ragazz)
lm3 <- lmer2lm(mixedm3)

mixedm4 <- lme(Olfactory ~ Dose + Sex, random=~Sex|Litter,
               weights = varIdent(form=~1|Dose), data=ragazz)
lm4 <- lmer2lm(mixedm4)

compare.medium.control <- glht(mmm(lm1, lm2, lm3, lm4),
```

```

mlf("DoseMedium = 0"))

MultMod<-summary(compare.medium.control)
MultModUnadjust<-summary(compare.medium.control, test = adjusted("none"))

```

	Mixed effect model	adjusted p-value	unadjusted p-value
1	lm1: DoseMedium	0.0249	0.0178
2	lm2: DoseMedium	0.0245	0.0181
3	lm3: DoseMedium	0.0240	0.0178
4	lm4: DoseMedium	0.0253	0.0185

Table 23: Comparing several mixed effect models

In this example, the simplest mixed model shows the smallest p-value. Only a small price is paid for considering several linear mixed models, see the unadjusted p-values in the object `MultModUnadjust`.

10 Simultaneous inference of composite endpoints with their individual endpoints

In confirmatory clinical trials a composite endpoint is used for efficacy claim when multiple correlated binary and/or time-to-event endpoints have to be considered. In cases where concerns about the clinical relevance as well as the individual interpretation of such composite endpoints may exist, the joint inference of the individual endpoints and the composite endpoint is recommended [SLD14]. By means of missing values modification of the mmm-approach such simultaneous confidence intervals for proportions can be estimated accordingly [RRH17]. As an example a two-arm intervention trial on osteoporosis with the composite endpoint of the both individual items 1) obtaining a BMD-test and 2) receiving an osteoporosis treatment in 262 patients.

```

library(multcomp)
## Define functions needed for calculation of local significance levels ## Corr: corr
alphaFct <- function(alpha, Corr, wei)
{
  q <- sapply(wei, function(x) qnorm(1-x*alpha/2))
  1 - as.numeric(pmvnorm(lower = -q, upper = q, mean = rep(0, length(q)),
                        corr = Corr))
}

adjAlphaFct <- function(Corr, wei = rep(1/nrow(Corr), nrow(Corr)), level = 0.05){
  # optimization on log scale for convenience
  objFct <- function(x) {log((alphaFct(x, Corr, wei) - level) + 1)}
  adjAlpha <- uniroot(objFct, interval = c(0.04, 1))["root"]
  localAlphas <- adjAlpha * wei
  localAlphas
}

```

```
## Loading required package: grid
##
## Attaching package: 'grid'
## The following object is masked from 'package:variables':
##
## unit
```


Figure 9: Mosaicplot osteoporosis trial.

```
## Marginal models: logistic regression for each endpoint
m1 <- glm(BMD ~ group, data = df, family = binomial)
m2 <- glm(Osteo ~ group, data = df, family = binomial)
m3 <- glm(CE ~ group, data = df, family = binomial)
## Extracting raw p-values
p.raw <- round(c(coef(summary(m1))[2,4], coef(summary(m2))[2,4], coef(summary
(m3))[2,4]), 4)

## Simultaneous analysis: comparison of treatment group to control group
library(multcomp)
fit <- glht(mmm(BMD=m1, Osteo=m2, CE=m3), mlf(mcp(group = "Dunnett")))
## Extract correlation matrix for parameters of interest
Sigma <- vcov(fit)
Corr <- cov2cor(Sigma)
## weighted alphas (weights: w1 = w2 = 0.25, w3 = 0.5)
level <- 0.05
wei <- c(0.25, 0.25, 0.5)
adj.alphas.unequal <- adjAlphaFct(Corr, wei)
## equally weighted alphas
wei <- rep(1/3, 3)
adj.alphas.equal <- adjAlphaFct(Corr, wei)
```

```

## calculate confidence intervals
betas <- coef(fit)
lower <- betas - qnorm(1-adj.alphas.equal)*sqrt(diag(Sigma))
upper <- betas + qnorm(1-adj.alphas.equal)*sqrt(diag(Sigma))
lower.unequal <- betas - qnorm(1-adj.alphas.unequal)*sqrt(diag(Sigma))
upper.unequal <- betas + qnorm(1-adj.alphas.unequal)*sqrt(diag(Sigma))
## transform confidence intervals to Odds Ratio
OR <- exp(betas)
lowerOR <- exp(lower)
upperOR <- exp(upper)
lowerOR.unequal <- exp(lower.unequal)
upperOR.unequal <- exp(upper.unequal)
confints <- matrix(round(c(OR, lowerOR, lowerOR.unequal),2),nrow =3, byrow = FALSE, c

```

	Odds ratio	lower limit	weighted lower limit
BMD-test	2.56	1.25	1.19
Osteop.treatment	2.11	0.51	0.46
Composite endpoint	2.36	1.17	1.24

We see a significant improvement in the composite endpoint and the individual endpoint BMD-test, but not in the second individual endpoint using this weighted or un-weighted simultaneous inference approach. In agronomy, related composite endpoints, such as harvest index are used as well [JSR20].

11 Conclusions

These different case studies show impressively: `mmm()` and `glht()` represent a new dimension of simultaneous inference - multiple models instead of only multiple contrasts.

Acknowledgement Drs. A. Kitsche (Hannover), M. Grosse-Ruse(Copenhagen), C. Vogel (Hannover), F. Konitschke (Berlin), T. Hothorn (Zurich), M. Hasler (Kiel), P. Pallmann (Cardiff), D. Gerhard (Christchurch), R. Ristl (Vienna), J. Kruppa (Berlin) contributes with CRAN packages and related publications to this topic.

References

- [AGM19] V. Amrhein, S. Greenland, and B. McShane. Retire statistical significance. *Nature*, 567(7748):305–307, March 2019.
- [AH09] M. Alosch and M. F. Huque. A flexible strategy for testing subgroups and overall population. *Statistics in Medicine*, 28(1):3–23, January 2009.
- [AR10] A. Agresti and E. Ryu. Pseudo-score confidence intervals for parameters in discrete statistical models. *Biometrika*, 97(1):215–222, March 2010.
- [BB10] W. Brannath and F. Bretz. Shortcuts for locally consonant closed test procedures. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 105(490):660–669, June 2010.
- [BG84] C. B. BEGG and R. GRAY. Calculation of polychotomous logistic-regression parameters using individualized regressions. *Biometrika*, 71(1):11–18, 1984.
- [BHH18] B. Brill, Y. Heller, and R. Heller. Nonparametric independence tests and k-sample tests for large sample sizes using package hhg. *R Journal*, 10(1):424–438, July 2018.
- [BMO⁺13] F. A. Beland, P. W. Mellick, G. R. Olson, M. C. B. Mendoza, M. M. Marques, and D. R. Doerge. Carcinogenicity of acrylamide in b6c3f(1) mice and f344/n rats from a 2-year drinking water exposure. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 51:149–159, January 2013.

- [BP88] A.J. Bailer and C. J. Portier. Effects of treatment-induced mortality and tumor-induced mortality on tests for carcinogenicity in small samples. *Biometrics*, 44(2):417–431, June 1988.
- [COX77] D. R. COX. Role of significance tests. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 4(2):49–70, 1977.
- [CS88] W. J. CONOVER and D. S. SALSBERG. Locally most powerful tests for detecting treatment effects when only a subset of patients can be expected to respond to treatment. *Biometrics*, 44(1):189–196, March 1988.
- [DEC⁺12] H. C. Diener, J. Eikelboom, S. J. Connolly, C. D. Joyner, R. G. Hart, G. Y. H. Lip, M. O’Donnell, S. H. Hohnloser, G. Hankey, O. Shestakovska, and S. Yusuf. Apixaban versus aspirin in patients with atrial fibrillation and previous stroke or transient ischaemic attack: a predefined subgroup analysis from averroes, a randomised trial. *Lancet Neurology*, 11(3):225–231, March 2012.
- [DM15] M. W. Donoghoe and I. C. Marschner. Flexible regression models for rate differences, risk differences and relative risks. *International Journal of Biostatistics*, 11(1):91–108, May 2015.
- [DSB03] S. Dudoit, J. P. Shaffer, and J. C. Boldrick. Multiple hypothesis testing in microarray experiments. *Statistical Science*, 18(1):71–103, February 2003.
- [Dun55] C. W. Dunnett. A multiple comparison procedure for comparing several treatments with a control. *J Am Stat Assoc*, 50(272):1096–1121, 1955.
- [ESD19] F. Emmert-Streib and M. Dehmer. Large-scale simultaneous inference with hypothesis testing: Multiple testing procedures in practice. *Mach. Learn. Knowl. Extr.*, 2019.
- [FB14] L. Finos and D. Basso. Permutation tests for between-unit fixed effects in multivariate generalized linear mixed models. *Statistics and Computing*, 24(6):941–952, November 2014.
- [GAB69] K. R. GABRIEL. Simultaneous test procedures - some theory of multiple comparisons. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 40(1):224–&, 1969.
- [GD07] S. Ghosh and G. De. Association analysis of population-based quantitative trait data: An assessment of anova. *Human Heredity*, 64(1):82–88, April 2007.
- [GYM13] J. Ganju, X. X. Yu, and G. G. Ma. Robust inference from multiple test statistics via permutations: a better alternative to the single test statistic approach for randomized trials. *Pharmaceutical Statistics*, 12(5):282–290, September 2013.
- [HBW08] T. Hothorn, F. Bretz, and P. Westfall. Simultaneous inference in general parametric models. *Biometrical Journal*, 50(3):346–363, June 2008.
- [HH08] M. Hasler and L. A. Hothorn. Multiple contrast tests in the presence of heteroscedasticity. *Biometrical Journal*, 50(5):793–800, October 2008.
- [HH09] L. A. Hothorn and T. Hothorn. Order-restricted scores test for the evaluation of population-based case-control studies when the genetic model is unknown. *Biometrical Journal*, 51(4):659–669, August 2009.
- [HH13] M. Hasler and L. A. Hothorn. Simultaneous confidence intervals on multivariate non-inferiority. *Statistics in Medicine*, 32(10):1720–1729, May 2013.
- [HKH20] L.A. Hothorn, J. Kruppa, and T. Hothorn. Multiple robust tests for genetic association with quantitative phenotypes. Technical report, LUH, 2020.
- [HL03] T. Hothorn and B. Lausen. On the exact distribution of maximally selected rank statistics. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 43(2):PII S0167–9473(02)00225–6, June 2003.
- [HMB18] T. Hothorn, L. Most, and P. Buhlmann. Most likely transformations. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 45(1):110–134, March 2018.
- [Hot16] L.A. Hothorn. *Statistics in Toxicology- using R*. Chapman Hall, 2016.
- [Hot19] T. Hothorn. 30 robust years. talk at leibniz university. 2019.
- [HSH10] E. Herberich, J. Sikorski, and T. Hothorn. A robust procedure for comparing multiple means under heteroscedasticity in unbalanced designs. *PLOS One*, 5(3):e9788, March 2010.
- [HZ08] T. Hothorn and A. Zeileis. Generalized maximally selected statistics. *Biometrics*, 64(4):1263–1269, December 2008.

- [JSR20] S. M. Jensen, J. Svendsgaard, and C. Ritz. Estimation of the harvest index and the relative water content - two examples of composite variables in agronomy. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 112:UNSP 125962, January 2020.
- [KBBH13] F. Konietzschke, S. Bosiger, E. Brunner, and L. A. Hothorn. Are multiple contrast tests superior to the anova? *International Journal of Biostatistics*, 9(1):63–73, May 2013.
- [KH14] A. Kitsche and L. A. Hothorn. Testing for qualitative interaction using ratios of treatment differences. *Statistics in Medicine*, 33(9):1477–1489, April 2014.
- [Kod12] R. L. Kodell. Should we assess tumorigenicity with the Peto or Poly-k test? *Statistics in Biopharmaceutical Research*, 4(2):118–124, May 2012.
- [KRH16] A. Kitsche, C. Ritz, and L. A. Hothorn. A general framework for the evaluation of genetic association studies using multiple marginal models. *Human Heredity*, 81(3):150–172, 2016.
- [KS15] A. Kitsche and F. Schaarschmidt. Analysis of statistical interactions in factorial experiments. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*, 201(1):69–79, February 2015.
- [L.19] Lin L. Statistical significance in high-dimensional linear mixed models. *arXiv:2019*, 2019.
- [LEH63] E. L. LEHMANN. Asymptotically nonparametric-inference - an alternative approach to linear-models. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 34(4):1494–+, 1963.
- [LR19] B. Liquet and J. Riou. Cpmcglm: an r package for p-value adjustment when looking for an optimal transformation of a single explanatory variable in generalized linear models. *Bmc Medical Research Methodology*, 19:79, April 2019.
- [LRFH41] T Lohse, S Rohrmann, D Faeh, and T Hothorn. Continuous outcome logistic regression for analyzing body mass index distributions. *F1000Research*, 2017, 6:1933 (doi: 10.12688/f1000research.12934.1).
- [MAK05] H. Moon, H. Ahn, and R. L. Kodell. An age-adjusted bootstrap-based poly-k test. *Statistics in Medicine*, 24(8):1233–1244, April 2005.
- [NBPD19] A. Neumann, T. Bodnar, D. Pfeifer, and T. Dickhaus. Multivariate multiple test procedures based on nonparametric copula estimation. *Biometrical Journal*, 61(1):40–61, January 2019.
- [Neu15] M. Neuhauser. Combining the t test and wilcoxon’s rank-sum test. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 42(12):2769–2775, December 2015.
- [NTP00] *National Toxicology Program. Toxicology and carcinogenesis studies of methyleugenol in F344/N rats and B6C3F1 mice.*, 2000.
- [PBGB14] J. Pinheiro, B. Bornkamp, E. Glimm, and F. Bretz. Model-based dose finding under model uncertainty using general parametric models. *Statistics in Medicine*, 33(10):1646–1661, May 2014.
- [PRB12] C. B. Pipper, C. Ritz, and H. Bisgaard. A versatile method for confirmatory evaluation of the effects of a covariate in multiple models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C-Applied Statistics*, 61:315–326, 2012.
- [PRH18] P. Pallmann, C. Ritz, and L. A. Hothorn. Simultaneous small-sample comparisons in longitudinal or multi-endpoint trials using multiple marginal models. *Statistics in Medicine*, 37(9):1562–1576, April 2018.
- [RHRP19] R. Ristl, L. Hothorn, C. Ritz, and M. Posch. Simultaneous inference for multiple marginal generalized estimating equation models. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*, page UNSP 0962280219873005, 2019.
- [RRH17] M. G. Ruse, C. Ritz, and L. A. Hothorn. Simultaneous inference of a binary composite endpoint and its components. *Journal of Biopharmaceutical Statistics*, 27(1):56–69, 2017.
- [SAH] J. Saul and K. Ashcroft-Hawley. Discussion on statistical analysis of carcinogenicity studies with an early terminated treated group. *Pharmaceutical Statistics*.
- [Sch13] F. Schaarschmidt. Simultaneous confidence intervals for multiple comparisons among expected values of log-normal variables. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 58:265–275, February 2013.
- [SGV17] F. Schaarschmidt, D. Gerhard, and C. Vogel. Simultaneous confidence intervals for comparisons of several multinomial samples. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 106:65–76, February 2017.
- [SH20] F. Schaarschmidt and L.A. Hothorn. library(tukeytrend). *Biometrics*, 2020.

- [SHI87] E. A. C. SHIRLEY. Applications of ranking methods to multiple comparison procedures and factorial-experiments. *Applied Statistics-journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C*, 36(2):205–213, 1987.
- [SLD14] A. J. Sankoh, H. H. Li, and R. B. D’Agostino. Use of composite endpoints in clinical trials. *Statistics in Medicine*, 33(27):4709–4714, November 2014.
- [SSH08] F. Schaarschmidt, M. Sill, and L. A. Hothorn. Approximate simultaneous confidence intervals for multiple contrasts of binomial proportions. *Biometrical Journal*, 50(5):782–792, October 2008.
- [TCH85] J. W. Tukey, J. L. Ciminera, and J. F. Heyse. Testing the statistical certainty of a response to increasing doses of a drug. *Biometrics*, 41(1):295–301, 1985.
- [VGPZ15] O. A. Vsevolozhskaya, M. C. Greenwood, S. L. Powell, and D. V. Zaykin. Resampling-based multiple comparison procedure with application to point-wise testing with functional data. *Environmental and Ecological Statistics*, 22(1):45–59, March 2015.
- [Vog18] C. Vogel. *Simultaneous Inference for the Comparison of Overdispersed Multinomial Data*. PhD thesis, Leibniz University Hannover, 2018.
- [Vog20] C. Vogel. (*submitted*), 2020.
- [Wes97] P. H. Westfall. Multiple testing of general contrasts using logical constraints and correlations. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 92(437):299–306, March 1997.
- [Wes99] P.H. et al Westfall. *Multiple Comparisons and Multiple Tests Using the SAS System*. SAS, 1999.
- [Wes11] P. H. Westfall. On using the bootstrap for multiple comparisons. *Journal of Biopharmaceutical Statistics*, 21(6):1187–1205, 2011.
- [Wil71] D.A. Williams. A test for differences between treatment means when several dose levels are compared with a zero dose control. *Biometrics*, 27(1):103–117, 1971.
- [WT08] P. H. Westfall and J. F. Troendle. Multiple testing with minimal assumptions. *Biometrical Journal*, 50(5):745–755, October 2008.
- [WY93] P. H. WESTFALL and S. S. YOUNG. On adjusting p-values for multiplicity. *Biometrics*, 49(3):941–944, September 1993.
- [ZLB⁺19] J. S. Zhu, S. Loubery, L. Broger, Y. J. Zhang, L. Lorenzo-Orts, A. Utz-Pugin, A. R. Fernie, C. Young-Tae, and M. Hothorn. A genetically validated approach for detecting inorganic polyphosphates in plants. *Plant Journal*, 2019.